

EVALUATION OF SKIN IRRITATION POTENTIAL OF AIRBORNE PARTICLES

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Abstract: *The aim of the study was to assess possible adverse effects generated by exposure to airborne particles, generated during the technological processing of fibers in textile processing units. Cutaneous irritation represents the biological response of the skin to a wide range of external stimuli that cause skin inflammation. The intact skin provides an effective barrier against bacteria, viruses and most exogenous chemicals, although it is still possible for very small particles to be able to pass the outer protective layer by diffusion, which can be enhanced if the skin is damaged. In this study, in order to assess the skin irritation potential of airborne particles, two different methods were used: DB-ALM Protocol n°138: In vitro, EpiDerm™ Skin Irritation Test (EpiDerm SIT), which uses human reconstituted dermis, supplied as viable cultures and ProQuantum immunoassay which is based on “leveraging proximity ligation assay” (PLA™) technology. The obtained results show that manufacturing residue in the form of micro or nanometric particles type material does not represent a major risk factor for dermal exposure on undamaged skin, whereas ProQuantum immunoassay revealed low levels of IL-1, suggesting a mild inflammatory reaction in exposed tissues, regardless of the overall classification as “non-irritant”.*

Keywords: *airborne particles; human dermis; inflammation; skin irritation, textile industry*

1. INTRODUCTION

Skin irritation is described as the production of reversible damage to the skin as a result of different conditions (disease, exposure to physical or chemical factors, etc.) and is evaluated by the application of a test substance/condition for up to 4 hours [1].

Although previously considered a monomorphic process, skin irritation is a complex biological event with a distinct pathophysiology, natural history and clinical appearance. The host reaction to the irritating exogenous agents has different clinical entities and is influenced by various factors of the irritating stimuli, environment and the host organism itself. The aim of the study was to assess possible adverse effects generated by exposure to airborne particles, generated during the technological processing of fibers in textile processing units [2].

For instance, airborne nanoparticles that are first released as single nanoparticles may later agglomerate and end on surfaces or the skin. Because skin contact with contaminated surfaces and objects is a key exposure pathway, the skin will therefore primarily come into contact with agglomerates of nanoparticles. When nanoparticles decrease in size, they can penetrate the skin more readily than when they were their original size [3].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The skin irritation potential of airborne particles collected from the textile industry was determined by testing micro/nanosuspension in isotonic saline solution of the samples collected from the textile workplaces using two different methods:

1) DB-ALM Protocol n°138: In vitro, EpiDerm™ Skin Irritation Test (EpiDerm SIT), using human reconstituted dermis, supplied as viable cultures. The positive control was 1% sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS). This model is an alternative test method, validated by ECVAM and is one of the recommended test models for the assessment of dermal irritation and corrosivity - Skin Irritation (OECD TG 439) and Corrosion (OECD TG 431) Testing [4]. According to the EU and GHS classification, an irritant is predicted if the average tissue viability of three individual tissues exposed to the test substance is below 50% compared to the relative viability of the negative controls; if the average tissue viability is below 15% compared to the relative viability of the negative controls, the product is declared corrosive. Therefore, the viability tests were performed for samples collected from the environment, in three series of independent replicates, with three sets of determinations in each independent replicate. Another route of exposure is the respiratory one. Since the respiratory route has physiological protection mechanisms, which allow the elimination of particles from the inhaled air we selected the dermal exposure route.

2) ProQuantum immunoassay which is based on “leveraging proximity ligation assay” (PLA™) technology. This assay is a combination of powerful proteomic tools, including high-specificity antibody–antigen binding and Invitrogen SiteClick antibody labelling, with genomic tools such as Applied Biosystems TaqMan® qPCR technology. Thus it is a detection method with both high sensitivity and a broad dynamic range. It requires minute sample volumes and can detect much lower levels of protein analytes than traditional methods. These immunoassays can quantify analytes over a concentration range of 5 orders of magnitude or more, minimizing the need for sample dilutions.

Both methods were carried out according to the protocols of the kits.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to the EU and GHS classification (category R38/Category 2 or no marking), an irritant is predicted if the average tissue viability of three individual tissues exposed to the test substance is below 50% compared to the relative viability of the negative controls; if the average tissue viability is below 15% compared to the relative viability of the negative controls, the product is declared corrosive (Table 1).

Table 1. EU and GHS classification

<i>In vitro</i> result	<i>In vivo</i> prediction
Mean tissue viability ≤50% (time of exposure 1h)	Irritant (I), (R38 or GHS 2 category)
Mean tissue viability >50% (time of exposure 1h)	Non-irritant (NI)

<i>In vitro</i> result	<i>In vivo</i> prediction
Mean tissue viability ≤15% (time of exposure 1h)	Corrosive (C)
Mean tissue viability >15% (time of exposure 1h)	Non-corrosive (NC)

Viability tests were performed, by applying the EPI-DERM system, for samples collected from the environment, in three series of independent replicates, with 3 sets of determinations in each independent replicate (Table 2).

Table 2. The data obtained according to EpiDermTM Skin Irritation Test

Product	Average DO	St.dev.	P ⁽³⁾	P ⁽⁴⁾	Relative viability (%)	Conclusion
PBS, ²	0,454	0,0271	-	-	100	
EtOH ²	0,439	0,0183	-	-	99,3	
SDS, ¹	0,057	0,0063	-	-	1,92	
Airborne particles – Sample 1, 88 mg/mL	0,174	0,00661	0,001	0,001	45,5	Non-Irritant (I)
Airborne particles – Sample 2, 84 mg/mL	0,174	0,00661	0,001	0,001	45,5	Non-Irritant (I)
Airborne particles – Sample 3, 92 mg/mL	0,174	0,00661	0,001	0,001	45,5	Non-Irritant (I)

1: positive control; 2: negative control; 3: Student t-test, 2-tailed, homoscedastic distribution, compared to negative control, 4: Student t-test 2-tailed, homoscedastic distribution, compared to positive control

According to the classification criteria, it is concluded that the tested products are non-irritant (NI) at an average concentration of 6.2 ± 0.808 mg/mL (the averages and SDs for the 3 distinct samples were 7.1 ± 0.2 , 5.5 ± 0.26 and 6.1 ± 0.56 mg/mL, respectively). Consequently, these nano- or micrometric airborne particles in the atmosphere/workspace do not constitute a major risk factor for the health of the personnel regarding skin irritation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Appearance of the kit after exposure and MTT viability assay – Left – Positive control (SDS) Right: Sample 2 (84 mg/mL)

Also, conducting the ProQuantum immunoassay on tissue lysates and supernatants of the EPi-Derm inserts made possible the detection and quantification of several cytokines produced by exposure to the samples.

PROQuantum assay is based on target-specific antibodies which are pre-conjugated to DNA oligonucleotides at either the 3' end (60 bases) or the 5' end (40 bases) of the nucleic acid. When the two antibodies are added to a sample suspension containing the specific protein, the two antibodies bind to their respective binding sites on the antigen, which results in the two oligonucleotide strands being brought in proximity. This antibody binding provides structural stability such that in the presence of DNA ligase and a third oligonucleotide connector (complementary to the ends of each of the original two DNA oligonucleotides), the two antibody-conjugated oligonucleotides are ligated together to create a 100-base strand, serving as a DNA amplification template. Following a temperature increase to 95°C to inactivate the ligase and denature the analyte proteins and antibodies, the DNA templates are amplified through 40 cycles of TaqMan fluorescence-based qPCR. The amount of DNA produced is measured after each amplification cycle via the fluorescence increase, which is directly proportional to the number of PCR product molecules (or amplicons) generated.

Figure 2. Monitoring of amplification

The presence of cytokines in supernatants (collected rapidly after the exposure to the samples) was significant, and was an indicator of some mild inflammatory effects of the samples on the dermis, although the overall classification was “non-irritant”. Performing the same assays on tissue lysates permitted only the detection of low levels of IL-1, most probably due to the original low levels of intracellular molecules and also, we speculate, to the low persistence of inflammation in exposed tissue (the products were classified as non-irritant), contrary to the positive control (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of exposure to tested products; sample volume: 10 µL using ProQuantum assays

Sample	Cytokine, (ng/mL)			
	IL-2	IFN-gamma	TNF-alpha	IL-1alpha
Control	N/D	N/D	N/D	N/D
Supernatant Sample 1	$1.6 \times 10^2 \pm 7$	$2.1 \times 10^2 \pm 7$	$3.1 \times 10^2 \pm 19$	$4 \times 10^2 \pm 52$
Supernatant Sample 2	$2.1 \times 10^2 \pm 12$	$3.9 \times 10^2 \pm 12$	$7.8 \times 10^2 \pm 27$	$5.4 \times 10^2 \pm 71$
Supernatant	$0.9 \times 10^2 \pm 6$	$1.4 \times 10^2 \pm 7$	$2.9 \times 10^2 \pm 22$	$3.4 \times 10^2 \pm 28$

Sample	Cytokine, (ng/mL)			
	IL-2	IFN-gamma	TNF-alpha	IL-1alpha
Sample 3				
Lysate S1	N/D	N/D	N/D	$.7 \times 10^2 \pm 2.1$
Lysate S2	N/D	N/D	N/D	$1.3 \times 10^2 \pm 3.9$
Lysate S3	N/D	N/D	N/D	$.6 \times 10^2 \pm 2.8$
Positive control (SN)	$1.7 \times 10^4 \pm 8 \times 10^2$	$4.9 \times 10^3 \pm 5 \times 10^2$	$6.7 \times 10^3 \pm 6 \times 10^2$	$1.2 \times 10^4 \pm 1.3 \times 10^3$
Positive control (Lysates)	$2.9 \times 10^3 \pm 2 \times 10^2$	$0.8 \times 10^3 \pm 93$	$1.2 \times 10^3 \pm 1.1 \times 10^2$	$2 \times 10^4 \pm .4 \times 10^3$

Conducting the ProQuantum immunoassay on tissue lysates and supernatants of the EPI-Derm inserts made possible the detection and quantification of several cytokines produced by exposure to the samples. The presence of cytokines in supernatants (collected rapidly after the exposure to the samples) was significant, and was an indicator of some mild inflammatory effects of the samples on the dermis, although the overall classification was “non-irritant”. Performing the same assays on tissue lysates permitted only the detection of low levels of IL-1, most probably due to the original low levels of intracellular molecules and also, we speculate, to the low persistence of inflammation in exposed tissue (the products were classified as non-irritant), contrary to the positive control.

4. CONCLUSION

The testing carried out allows the conclusion that the “manufacturing residue in the form of micro or nanometric particles” type material does not represent a major risk factor for dermal exposure on undamaged skin. However, a higher risk is not excluded when exposed to open wounds or in the case of exposures caused by intake by other routes (for example, respiratory).

ProQuantum immunoassay revealed low levels of IL-1, suggesting a mild inflammatory reaction in exposed tissues, regardless of the overall classification as “non-irritant”.

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